

The cost of Open Access: Public funding investment in APCs in Spain

Pablo Sastron-Toledo¹, Patricia Alonso-Alvarez², Jorge Mañana-Rodríguez³

¹*psastron@bib.uc3m.es*, ²*patalons@bib.uc3m.es*

Carlos III University of Madrid, LEMI Research Group, 126 Madrid Str., 28903, Getafe, (Spain)
Carlos III University of Madrid, Research Institute for Higher Education and Science (INAECU), 126 Madrid Str., 28903, Getafe, (Spain)

³*jmanana@pa.uc3m.es*

Carlos III University of Madrid, Research Institute for Higher Education and Science (INAECU), 126 Madrid Str., 28903, Getafe, (Spain)

Abstract

Open access publication often entails payment of Article Processing Charges (APCs), particularly in the so-called Hybrid and Gold journals. The growth of Gold OA publications linked to the development of open access mandates has forced funding institutions to take over APCs. Thus, this research seeks to quantify the amount of public investment dedicated to APC within the projects funded by the Spanish State Plan for the Generation of Knowledge and Scientific and Technological Strengthening of the R&D&I (SNP), the main public research funding instrument in Spain. The period studied is 2013-2018. The preliminary results show that 20,399 million € were spent on APCs, accounting for 1.5% of the total budget funded by the SNP. In addition, the average percentage of the budget dedicated to cover APCs has been calculated for a sample of projects. Most research areas are dedicated between 0-5% of their budget to cover APCs. However, numerous outliers with rates over 10% suggest further study on the role of APCs in the financial performance of the research activity.

Introduction

The scientific literature reflects the growth of open access (hereafter OA) publications, especially Gold OA (Björk et al., 2010; Khoo, 2019). Gold and Hybrid OA routes imply immediately making openly available an article preceded by the payment of Article Processing Charges (APCs). Journals with APCs comprise 30% of the OA journals but publish 56% of the research (Crawford, 2018). APCs' prices present great variability, but generally, the journals' factor (JIF hereafter) and prestige are positively correlated to the APCs' price (Björk & Solomon, 2015; Pollock & Michael, 2019).

The rapid growth of OA and its incidence in the free online availability of research crystallized into a series of so-called OA mandates. These mandates are normative documents developed by policymakers and research-funding organizations. They contain regulations on the OA publication of funded research. As an example of the early adoption of OA mandates, the UK Higher Education Funding Council (HEFCE) requested an immediate deposit of peer-reviewed articles funded by the Council in institutional repositories since 2013. Several precedents and many other later examples of country-level mandates are available in the Registry of Open Access Repositories Mandatory Archiving Policies (ROARMAP, available at: <https://roarmap.eprints.org/>). The requirement of publishing in OA implied the payment of APCs to access Gold and Hybrid journals. To adapt to this new reality, research funding agencies started covering APCs fees in the early 2000s (Tananbaum, 2003). The assumption of publication costs by funding agencies has a key precedent in the European Commission Pilot initiative to fund APCs associated with finished FP7 projects (FP7 Post-Grant Open Access Pilot), allowing in some cases (OpenAIRE) the joint negotiation of APC prices. The findings of Aasheim et al., 2019 indicate that the APCs paid by European institutions have nearly doubled from 2005 to 2018. Quadery et al. (2019) also estimate that a redirection of €150 million to the journals publishing publicly funded research would be necessary to accomplish Plan S, a cost that research funders would ultimately assume. A recent study by Butler et al.

(2022) estimates the paid APC fees acknowledging funding from the Canadian Tri-Agency and other Canadian Federal Funding Agencies between 2015 and 2018. Their estimation lists the expenditure as \$27.6 million.

In Spain, the Spanish State Plan for the Generation of Knowledge and Scientific and Technological Strengthening of the R&D&I (SNP hereafter), which is Spain's main research public funding instrument, includes specific APC cover for funded research as a budgetary in the proposals' scheme. Whereas several studies have analyzed the expenditure in APCs by research funding organizations, the data for the SNP is unknown. For instance, a recent study by Consorcio Madroño (2020) (a network of 6 universities from the Madrid Autonomous Region) estimated that €1,926,643 was spent on the coverage of APCs in 2019. This project aims to estimate the amount of funds that are expended in APCs by the SNP. In this Research in Progress, we present the initial results of ongoing research for the case of SNP between 2013 and 2018. We also briefly study the average percentage of APCs paid per project and research areas.

Data

Several datasets were used to conduct this research:

- SNP projects dataset: a dataset containing all the information of the projects accepted from 2013 to 2018.
- Publications dataset: a dataset containing all the articles published due to the financed projects.
- APC datasets: a set of different datasets containing information about the cost of APC in different journals.

The retrieving information process is detailed in the sections below.

SNP projects data

SNP-funded projects were obtained by downloading the project award resolutions on the Spanish National Research Agency's website. These resolutions are in PDF format; therefore, the data was previously structured using the Python library `tabula.py`. Finally, information was obtained on 16,848 projects from 2013 to 2018, a total amount of 1,995 million euros financed. The dataset contains information related to the projects, such as funding, institution, research area, and grant number. We did not include projects funded after 2018 as the publication of results is not immediate and varies depending on research fields and other factors. We consider four years as the average period needed to publish results due to the SNP project's duration varying between 3 and 4 years.

Publications dataset

Articles from SNP-funded projects were retrieved from Clarivate Analytics Web of Science (WoS) - 'Core Collection' and Science, Social Sciences and Arts & Humanities Citation Indexes (SCI, SSCI, AHCI, and ESCI) databases - using the funding acknowledgments field. This field was cross-referenced with the SNP grant numbers, thus obtaining the scientific production of each project awarded. We retrieved 104,833 publications for the period 2013-2018.

APC datasets

The information on the cost of the APCs of the journals comes from three different sources (based on the approach defined by Butler et al., 2022):

- The first dataset contains APC information registered in the OpenAPC initiative (<https://openapc.net/>), a non-profit platform aggregating voluntary data from research

institutions. Open APC offers data on the cost of all APCs per article paid by the collaborating partners. As APCs for the same journal and year vary depending on the reporter agency, we calculated the minimum APC paid per journal per year and used it for the analysis, so costs are not overestimated.

- The second dataset (Matthias, 2020) contains the APC cost of ten publishers (Cambridge, Copernicus, Elsevier, Hindawi, Nature, Oup, Sage, Springer-Nature, Taylor & Francis, and Wiley). This information was retrieved from the publishers' webpages through the Internet Archive's Wayback Machine, thus reflecting the different prices of APCs over time. For more information on the APCs' retrieval process, refer to Matthias (2020). Once the data was processed, the dataset contained a combination of 65,803 journal-year.
- The third dataset (Morrison, 2021) contains mainly APC listed on the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ, <https://doaj.org/>). Butler et al. (2022) also point out that the information of this dataset includes "a previous dataset from DOAJ, Crawford (2019), DOAJ, OpenAPC and Morrison (2019), including frequent manual checks on journal websites". For more information on the APCs' retrieval process, refer to Morrison (2021). Once the data was processed, the dataset contained a combination of 102,860 journal-year.

Methodology

Once the information on the SNP-funded projects was retrieved and their resultant publications identified, we calculated the cost on APC for each OA article published in Gold and Hybrid journals. APCs were assigned to each article, taking into account the journal and the year of publication. When the year of the publication was not available, the average APC of the journal within the years captured was assigned.

A criterion was established to cross-reference the publications with their APCs cost in an iterative process. We first used the OpenAPC database since it is the dataset that matches the highest number of publications, and the APCs are registered in the same currency as the project funding (euros). Then, Matthias (2020) and Morrison (2020) (based on the matching preference observed in Butler et al., 2022) APCs were converted to euros (taking into account the value of the year of the given journal) and cross-referenced with the remaining records.

A total of 66,470 publications were published in OA (63,4% of the total number of publications produced by the projects). Half of them were published in Gold journals (25,151) and Hybrid journals (5,834). These publications (30,985) were cross-referenced with the APC datasets resulting in a total of 25,453 matched publications (82%). Therefore, the results underestimate the actual expense of APC in the studied period. Future research may focus on improving this ratio and include the data that has not matched, thus improving the existing databases.

Results

Total sample (66,470 publications)

The analysis reveals that 25,453 publications APCs were published in 1,302 Gold journals and 1,593 Hybrid journals. The publication of these articles cost a total of €43,910 million spent in APCs from 2013 to 2018: €32,006 million in Gold journals and €11,904 million in Hybrid journals. In sum, these costs accounted for 2,2% of the total budget financed by the SNP from 2013 to 2018.

Sample with projects with all OA publications matched with APC (25,453publications)

A sample was extracted to get a more accurate picture of the percentage of funding that APCs represent within a project's budget. The sample contained all the projects whose publications' APCs were covered by our database (8,969 projects, 53% of the total projects). Figure 1 illustrates the ratio of APC-projects budget within the different research areas. Research areas are based on the categorization of areas of the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (<https://www.aei.gov.es/areas-tematicas/areas-tematicas>). The average share of projects funding spent in APCs tends to be between 0-5%. In the case of Law, this fact is biased by the small amount of money for the projects (see Table 1 in Appendix 1).

There are plenty of projects where the amount of APC exceeded half of the project's budget. These high ratios are due to the small amount of project funding and the large number of articles published. For example, the budgets of the project in the areas of Economics, which dedicated an 80,9% to APCs is €21,780. The project acknowledged 52 articles, between 2018 and 2020 (a number of articles higher than the average in their research area, see Appendix 1). In the case of Physics, the average number of publications per project is 20, so for those projects with low budgets (i.e., theoretical physics), it is easy to spend high percentages of the budget with APC.

*Both "History and Art" and "Philosophy and Philology" were replaced in 2018 by the areas "Language, mind and thought" and "History and Archeology." Both denominations are presented because they are not strictly equivalent

Figure 1. Percentage of APC paid per project for the different ANEP areas.

Discussion

In publicly funded projects, the costs of OA publishing are considered under the projects' budget. As OA publishing grows, it implies that research agencies will spend higher amounts of money on paying APCs. Thus, this research in progress aims to know the public money spent on APCs within the Spanish National Plan. Although the APCs data has to be refined and more journals need to be added, we found that at least €43,910million were transferred to different publishers to pay for APCs in projects awarded between 2013 and 2018. This amount is

practically equivalent to the investment allocated to the area of social sciences within the SNP for the period studied (€46,493million). However, the value is underestimated due to the percentage of Gold and Hybrid publications for which APC information was obtained (82%). The following steps of this project will try to obtain the costs of APCs for the remaining articles to get a more accurate perspective of APCs' expenses in Spain.

One limitation of this study relies on the relation between the projects acknowledged in each publication and the subsequent payment of APCs. These publications APCs do not necessarily come from the projects budgets as there are other ways to finance these costs (i.e. transformative agreements, budgets from other projects, institutional funds). Although the percentage of money allocated to APCs constitutes a small amount of the projects' funds, the total quantity is not negligible, especially considering the ongoing discussion on double dipping (Pinfield et al., 2015).

When analyzing only the sample of projects fully covered by the database, we see that the average in most areas is between 0 and 5% of the total funding of the projects. However, the numbers are higher in some areas. This fact raises questions about the role of SNP funding in the research activity. First, are all the publications that acknowledge SNP projects related to the project's purpose and objectives? If public money is being spent on APCs, it is essential to know that the publications are related to the topic of the projects. These questions have to be addressed from a qualitative perspective in future research to improve the tracking process of scientific outputs. Secondly, is the funding granted enough to cover all research-related and OA publication costs? In this sense, publishing in OA might be restricted to researchers with enough funds to pay APCs. Previous research has warned about the inequities that the APC model may involve (Klebel & Ross-Hellauer, 2022), especially for countries in the global South. In this sense, national case studies, such as this one, may contribute to studies on the harmful effects fostered by the APC model.

Acknowledgments

This study was funded under an FPI contract PRE2020-092917 of the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation from the DOSSUET project (Diagnosis of open science in the Spanish university system and mechanisms for its transformation and improvement) grant number PID2019-104052RB-C21.

References

- Aasheim, J.H., Ahlborn, B., Ambler, C., Andrae, M., Apel, J., Becker, H.-G., Young, P. (2019). *Datasets on fee-based open access publishing across German institutions*. Bielefeld University. <https://doi.org/10.4119/UNIBI/UB.2014.18>.
- Agencia Estatal de Investigación. Áreas Temáticas. <https://www.aei.gob.es/areas-tematicas/areas-tematicas> Retrieved: 23/11/2022
- Björk, B. C., Welling, P., Laakso, M., Majlender, P., Hedlund, T., & Guðnason, G. (2010). Open access to the scientific journal literature: situation 2009. *PloS one*, 5(6), e11273.
- Björk, B.-C., & Solomon, D. (2015). Article processing charges in OA journals: the relationship between price and quality. *Scientometrics*, 103(2), 373–385. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-015-1556>.
- Butler, L. A., Matthias, L., Simard, M. A., Mongeon, P., & Haustein, S. (2022, August). The oligopoly's shift to open access publishing: How for-profit publishers benefit from gold and hybrid article processing charges. In *Proceedings of the Annual Conference of CAIS/Actes du congrès annuel de l'ACSI*.

- Consortio Madroño (2020). *Estimación de costes de publicación en Acceso Abierto, por pago de APC (Article Processing Charges), asociados al Consortio Madroño durante los años 2018 y 2019*. Available at <https://e-archivo.uc3m.es/handle/10016/31213#preview>
- Crawford, W. (2018). *GOAJ3: Gold open access journals 2012–2017*. Livermore, California: Cites & Insights Books
- Khoo, S. (2019). Article processing charge hyperinflation and price insensitivity: An open access sequel to the serials crisis. *Liber Quarterly*, 29(1).
- Klebel, T., & Ross-Hellauer, T. (2022). The APC-Effect: Stratification in Open Access Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.31222/osf.io/w5szk>
- Pinfield, S. (2013). Is scholarly publishing going from crisis to crisis? *Learned Publishing*, 26(2), 85–88. <https://doi.org/10.1087/20130204>.
- Pinfield, S., Salter, J., & Bath, P. A. (2015). The “total cost of publication” in a hybrid open-access environment: Institutional approaches to funding journal article-processing charges in combination with subscriptions. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, (In press). Retrieved from <http://eprints.whiterose.ac.uk/81227/>
- Pollock, D., & Michael, A. (2019). Open access mythbusting: Testing two prevailing assumptions about the effects of open access adoption. *Learned Publishing*, 32(1), 7–12. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1209>.
- Quaderi, N., Hardcastle, J., Petrou, C., & Szomszor, M. (2019). *The Plan S footprint: Implications for the scholarly publishing landscape*. Institute for Scientific Information Working Paper. Available at: <https://beopen-project.eu/storage/files/ws190021-isi-report-2019-013.pdf>
- Tananbaum, G. (2003). Of wolves and and boys: the scholarly communication crisis. *Learned Publishing*, 16(4), 285–289. <https://doi.org/10.1087/095315103322422035>.
- West, J. D., Bergstrom, T., & Bergstrom, C. T. (2014). Cost effectiveness of open access publications. *Economic Inquiry*, 52(4), 1315-1321.

Appendix 1

Table 1. Average project's budget in euros per research area

<i>Research Area</i>	<i>Average project's budget €</i>	<i>Average publications per project</i>
Biomedicine (n=954)	219.013	8
Life science and Biotechnology (n=1,001)	212.440	7
Physics (n=718)	177.783	21
Agriculture and food-science (n=780)	155.524	9
Environmental Science (n=912)	149.410	11
Chemical Science (n=695)	146.061	19
Energy and Transport (n=266)	137.103	11
Materials science (n=565)	132.492	19
Industrial and civil engineering (n=467)	128.257	10
ICT (n=943)	124.024	13
Sports (n=48)	74.369	11
Psychology (n=353)	66.439	8
History and Archeology (n=7)*	59.463	2
Mathematics (n=308)	58.984	23
History and Art (n=91)*	58.587	7
Philology and Philosophy (n=78)*	52.112	7
Social Sciences (n=169)	49.706	5
Language, mind and thought (n=10)*	46.948	3
Education (n=93)	41.418	6
Economics (n=290)	35.843	12
Law (n=19)	25.098	4